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D5.3 Economic Analysis: Calculation of CAPEX, OPEX and overall levelized cost for hydrogen production and energy storage

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Document Summary

This document performs an economic analysis of the ALFRED reactor integrated with either molten salt thermal energy storage or high-temperature steam electrolysis plant. It reviews literature on the economics of lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs), focusing on specific capital costs and levelized cost of electricity, noting significant uncertainties. The report analyzes the economic merit of molten salt thermal energy storage coupled with LFRs, using cost estimation models, and a discounted cash flow analysis. It identifies the most cost-effective reactor configurations and estimates that a daily electricity price fluctuation of around 100 \$/MWh is needed for profitability. Similarly, the document evaluates the electrolysis plant's costs, determining the optimal hydrogen production schedule to minimize costs. Producing hydrogen for 16-18 hours per day is found to reduce costs to approximately 4-6 \$/kg, considering capital, operational, and opportunity costs.

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List of acronyms

ALFRED	Advanced Lead Fast Reactor European Demonstrator
ANSELMUS	Advanced Nuclear Safety Evaluation of Liquid Metals Using Systems
BOP	Balance-Of-Plant
CAPEX	CAPital EXPediture
DC	Direct Costs
DCF	Discounted cash flow
FOAK	First-Of-A-Kind
HTSE	High-Temperature Steam Electrolysis
IC	Indirect costs
LBE	Lead-Bismuth Eutectic
LCOE	Levelized Cost Of Electricity
LFR	Lead-cooled Fast Reactor
LWR	Light Water Reactor
MSTES	Molten Salt Thermal Energy Storage
MYRRHA	Multi-purpose hYbrid Research Reactor for High-tech Applications
NOAK	Nth-Of-A-Kind
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
NPV	Net Present Value
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OPEX	OPERational EXPediture
PC	Pre-construction costs
SMR	Small Modular Reactor
TCI	Total Capital Investment
TPH	Total Produced Hydrogen
USD	United States Dollars

1 Introduction

In this work, economic analyses regarding lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs) are presented, with a focus on the ALFRED demonstrator. Its integration with thermal energy storage by molten salt or with the possibility of hydrogen cogeneration through high-temperature steam electrolysis were analyzed.

At first, in section [2](#), a systematic literature review of the economics of LFRs was performed. The state-of-the-art in both scientific and industrial literature was summarized, retrieving ranges for the specific capital costs and levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) for LFRs. These values incorporate large uncertainties due to almost inexistent experience in building and operating LFRs. In section [3](#), the economic analysis of ALFRED integrated with a molten salt thermal energy storage (MSTES) was performed. The capital and operational expenditures (CAPEX and OPEX) were estimated, by retrieving data and models from literature and the increase in revenues brought by the MSTES based on data from 2023 for electricity prices. Also, the economic merit of this integration employing a discounted cash flow (DCF) was evaluated. In section [4](#), the hydrogen cogeneration by high-temperature steam electrolysis (HTSE) was considered. As in the previous analysis, CAPEX and OPEX by retrieving data and using models from the literature were estimated. Also, the opportunity cost (i.e., loss of revenues given that the nuclear plant is not selling electricity but using it to produce hydrogen), was included. For this last cost, 5 years of electricity price data (2019-2023) were taken into account. The hydrogen cost for any arbitrary period was determined, thus, the optimal production period that minimizes hydrogen cost was obtained.

These economic analyses are based on previous work in the ANSELMUS project, as follows:

- Deliverable 5.1 [\[1\]](#), which defines the final system configurations, particularly the ALFRED reactor coupled with MSTES, or with an HTSE plant for hydrogen cogeneration based on solid oxide electrolysis cell type;
- Deliverable 5.2 [\[2\]](#), which analyses in detail all the configurations, particularly ALFRED by itself, 18 for ALFRED coupled with MSTES, and 4 configurations for ALFRED coupled with HTSE;
- Milestone 23 [\[6\]](#), which summarizes the appropriate inputs that will be used in these economic analyses.

Throughout this document, all costs and prices are expressed in USD (\$) as of 2022.

2 Economic Considerations on LFRs

Despite being one of the six Gen IV technologies and most researched advanced nuclear technology, LFRs are often not analyzed from an economical standpoint. A systematic literature review of LFR economics [3] was performed, considering both scientific and industrial literature, for pure lead and lead-bismuth eutectic (LBE) technology. Only a handful of documents referred to such topics, often giving heterogeneous information. The retrieved documents greatly varied considering the assumptions they made, the types of calculation, and the overall objectives of the document (most of the time the economic analysis is a secondary aspect).

The specific capital cost (i.e., per unit of electricity produced) and LCOE expressed in \$/kWe and \$/MWh respectively were considered, to compare all the retrieved documents. These costs are the most common indicators in the literature, and most documents report them directly or can be easily computed. Values of 1.5-25 k\$/kWe and 30-350 \$/MWh for the specific capital cost and the LCOE respectively, were found. The uncertainties embedded in these values are over one order of magnitude, as reported in fig. 1 and 2 [3]. This is due to limited experience in LFR construction (only the demonstrator BREST-OD-300 which is under construction in Russia [9]), and almost nonexistent in operation.

Fig. 1. Specific capital cost of the retrieved documents with their uncertainties [3]

Fig. 2. Levelized cost of electricity of the retrieved documents with their uncertainties [3]

The capital cost is driven by the plant size and economy-of-scale. The larger the plant, the higher the costs, but the lower the specific costs. For small nuclear plants, this economic deficit could be compensated by lower overall expenses, faster construction, a higher learning rate (at the same site, within the country, and globally), co-siting economies (sharing fixed construction costs), a simpler and inherently safe design, and modular factory-build components. These aspects should be accounted for in the cost evaluation of LFR NPPs. However, it is impossible to estimate LFR cost accounts with reasonable certainty at this stage. We should also consider that economic analyses based on highly uncertain data or estimates typically have low practical value.

The cost structure of an NPP is capital-intensive, meaning it is dominated by the overnight capital cost and its associated interests (both during construction and operation), while fuel cycle, operation and maintenance (O&M), and decommissioning costs account for a smaller fraction. For LFRs, how they drift from the values expected for conventional NPP is an open question. They depend on the country in which the LFR NPP is built and its experience with nuclear construction. A country that is already building NPPs would have a better estimate of construction costs and time compared to a country that has stopped such projects. Newcomers would likely rely on foreign experience to mitigate the risk of over-budget and delayed LFR projects. Such estimates could be highly uncertain, also considering the various LFR size possibilities. For example, ALFRED is a 120 MWe reactor, newcleo is considering the LFR-AS-30 and the LFR-AS-200 (30 and 200 MWe, respectively) [10], BREST-OD-300 is a Russian 300 MWe demonstrator currently under construction [9]. Additionally, smaller modular LFRs could also be an option. For smaller plants, we should expect a larger fraction of overnight capital cost. However, due to the expected shorter construction period, the cost of capital may be reduced at the same interest rate. Nevertheless, higher interest rates are likely, especially for the first-of-a-kind (FOAK) projects, due to the innovative nature of the technology and the uncertainties associated with the

construction process. Nth-of-a-kind (NOAK) plants would significantly benefit from the accumulated experience and the reduced risks associated with construction and operation.

The operability of LFRs is still unknown. By examining a demonstrator (ALFRED or the Russian BREST-OD-300), we can draw insights from similar plants, e.g., Phénix [8]. Reference [8] provides a detailed history of planned and unplanned reactor shutdowns (reaching up to two unscheduled shutdowns per 1000 hours of grid connection), as well as the overall operational experience gained from the reactor. However, it also mentions that the Russian BN-600, after overcoming its initial teething problems, could reach a load factor of 70% [8]. Similarly, for an LFR demonstrator, we could expect a high number of unplanned shutdowns caused by factors such as operating incidents, power loss, failure of control instrumentation or equipment, and human errors [8]. Therefore, ALFRED is expected to have particularly high O&M costs. The operability of LFRs remains highly uncertain, and ALFRED will play a crucial role in understanding and reducing these uncertainties. As commercial FOAK and NOAK plants develop, they will likely achieve greater efficiency and lower specific costs. Other cost factors, such as fuel cycle and decommissioning costs, are challenging to estimate due to their uncertainties, especially given the potential for a closed fuel cycle.

3 Economic Analysis of LFRs coupled with Molten Salt Thermal Energy Storage

3.1 ALFRED integrated with MSTES

The configurations considered in this study are detailed in [2], with a total of 18 configurations. Tab. 1 summarizes the main characteristics of configurations taken into account. Three possible tank sizes (S1, S2, and S3), three unloading schemes (U1, U2, and U3), each paired with a turbine of different size, and two loading schemes (L1 and L2) were analyzed [2]. An example of a possible configuration is 'U2L1S3' and the considered salt is solar salt with a mass composition of 40% KNO₃ and 60% NaNO₃ [2].

Tab.1. Main characteristics of the configurations of ALFRED coupled with MSTES [2]

Reactor	LFR	ALFRED: 300 MWt, 118 MWe.
Loading and Unloading Schemes	U1L1	Net power when loading and unloading: 80.6 and 136.0 MWe. Unloading/loading time ratio: 1.44.
	U1L2	Net power when loading and unloading: 41.5 and 136.0 MWe. Unloading/loading time ratio: 2.87.
	U2L1	Net power when loading and unloading: 73.6 and 153.6 MWe. Unloading/loading time ratio: 0.72.
	U2L2	Net power when loading and unloading: 35.0 and 153.6 MWe. Unloading/loading time ratio: 1.43.
	U3L1	Net power when loading and unloading: 68.3 and 187.1 MWe. Unloading/loading time ratio: 0.36.
	U3L2	Net power when loading and unloading: 30.1 and 187.1 MWe. Unloading/loading time ratio: 0.72.
Tanks	S1	Total salt: 12000 ton. Diameter: 24.2 m. Height: 14 m.
	S2	Total salt: 15000 ton. Diameter: 27.1 m. Height: 14 m.
	S3	Total salt: 20000 ton. Diameter: 31.3 m. Height: 14 m.

The methodology used in this economic analysis and the hypothesis could be summarized as follows:

- *Reference plant.* The base plant is ALFRED NPP by itself, not coupled with MSTES. This is the base value, or 'zero', of the following economic analysis. With the MSTES, the reactor can maintain a constant thermal power.
- *Differential analysis.* We estimated the increase in revenues, capital, and operational costs from the reference plant generated by the coupling with the MSTES. Thus, we can evaluate the economic benefit of adding the MSTES to the plant. The question this analysis answers is whether it would be possible to recover the additional investment for the MSTES considering exclusively the additional revenues it generates.
- *Code of accounts.* A code of accounts was developed, to perform a bottom-up estimation of the costs. We considered the plant as a FOAK. We estimated MSTES direct and indirect costs (DC and IC respectively, their sum being the total capital investment, TCI), MSTES O&M costs, and the increase in capital cost of ALFRED BOP. The code of account is detailed in the [Appendix](#). The account costs were estimated from data and models found in the literature.
- *Price arbitrage.* Molten salt is loaded during the lowest electricity price hours and unloaded (producing more steam and electrical power) when electricity prices are high. For simplicity, the loading time is an integred hour, the unloading time is computed with the ratios in tab. 1.
- *Countries.* We considered the day-ahead hourly electricity price of 2023 in France, Germany, Italy, and Romania, resulting in a total of 72 possible scenarios (18 configurations * 4 countries). Such data is retrieved from [5].
- *1-day approximation.* We considered a single day as representative of electricity prices for the entire. Specifically, the price at hour 'n' of the average day is calculated as the average of the

prices at hour 'n' across all 365 days of the year. The average daily electricity prices for the countries are represented in fig. 3. Despite losing the seasonality of electricity prices and the differences between weekdays and weekends, we applied this approximation for simplicity: the analysis became daily instead of annual. In this scenario, we also assumed that the total amount of salt loaded (in a day) equals the total amount unloaded. With this approximation, the NPP integrated with the MSTES would only bid in the day-ahead market and not in the intraday one, which could be highly remunerative.

- Revenues.** The total increase in daily revenues is the sum of the opportunity cost of loading the salt (i.e., electricity not sold but used to load the MSTES) and the additional revenue generated by increasing production during the unloading phase when electricity prices are higher. This sum must exceed the daily O&M costs and tanks cannot be fully loaded or unloaded. Revenues are computed assuming perfect knowledge of the day-ahead market. We do not consider other markets that could also be profitable. From fig. 3, we can see that all the curves exhibit a 'duck shape'. Romania shows a higher increase on average during evening hours, suggesting that all the configurations would be more profitable there. France has an overall less variable profile. Italy has the highest electricity prices; however, to evaluate the economic benefit of the MSTES, we consider variations from the average value and not the actual electricity prices.
- Discounted cash flow.** We performed the economic analysis using a discounted cash flow (DCF) over 30 years, assuming that the nuclear part of the plant is already operational, and computing the net present values (NPVs) of different configurations. The construction of the MSTES lasts 2 years, while its dismantling is 1 year (years 1-2 and year 30, respectively). The initial investment is equally divided over the construction years. From years 3 to 29, the cash outflows correspond to O&M costs, while cash inflows represent the maximum revenue increase multiplied by a 90% load factor. The interest rate is fixed at 5% for all countries.

Fig. 3. Average days of electricity prices in 2023

We now present the results of the analysis. Tab. 2 summarizes the estimated costs for all 18 configurations. The Appendix provides detailed computations of these values, which are independent of the country. The total increase in capital cost, considering the MSTES and the increase in NPP cost, ranges between 85 and 154 M\$. The least expensive configuration is U1L1S1 while the most expensive is U3L2S3. The annual O&M costs for the MSTES range between 3 and 5 M\$.

Similarly, fig. 4 presents the maximum daily revenue increase for the configurations in the specific country. The configuration with the highest revenue increase is U3L2S3, reaching 27-39 k\$/day, depending on the country. Note that only 31 out of the 72 total possibilities are reported. This occurs for two reasons:

- The increase in revenues is lower than the daily O&M in 31 cases, such as for U1 configurations in France, Germany, and Italy.
- Some configurations yield the same maximum revenues as those with smaller tanks. This occurs 10 times, for example, U2S3 configurations generate the same maximum revenues as U2S2 ones because the larger tanks are not exploited.

Tab. 2. Results of the cost estimations for the 18 MSTES configurations

[M\$]	MSTES				NPP	Total increase in capital cost (MSTES+NPP)		MSTES				NPP	Total increase in capital cost (MSTES+NPP)
	DC	IC	TCI	Annual O&M costs				DC	IC	TCI	Annual O&M costs		
U1L1S1	61	16	76	3	9	85	U2L2S1	69	18	87	3	17	104
U1L1S2	68	17	85	3	9	94	U2L2S2	77	20	97	4	17	114
U1L1S3	85	22	106	4	9	105	U2L2S3	87	22	109	4	17	126
U1L2S1	67	17	84	3	9	93	U3L1S1	75	19	94	4	32	126
U1L2S2	74	19	92	4	9	101	U3L1S2	80	21	101	4	32	133
U1L2S3	91	23	114	5	9	123	U3L1S3	91	23	115	5	32	147
U2L1S1	63	16	79	3	17	96	U3L2S1	81	21	101	4	32	133
U2L1S2	71	18	89	4	17	106	U3L2S2	87	22	109	4	32	141
U2L1S3	81	21	102	4	17	119	U3L2S3	98	25	122	5	32	154

Legend	S1	S2	S3	Countries	
U1L1				France	Germany
U2L1				◊	◻
U3L1					
U1L2				Italy	Romania
U2L2				Δ	○
U3L2					

Fig. 4. Maximum daily increase in revenues for the MSTES configurations

We performed the DCF only for the configurations that were not excluded. Tab. 3 presents the NPVs obtained from the DCF. Note that all scenarios resulted in a negative NPV, indicating that, in these scenarios, the increase in revenues is not sufficient to fully recover the additional investment and O&M costs over the 30 years. For Germany and Romania, the configuration with the highest NPV is U3L2S3, for France and Italy it is U2L1S1. However, despite not having the highest NPV in all cases, U3L2S3 could still be considered a promising option due to its potential for improvement. This aspect will become clearer in the following paragraphs and thanks to fig. 6. Among the analyzed configurations, U3L2S3 requires the lowest increase in revenues (or cost reduction) to reach positive NPVs. Thus, we can argue that U3L2S3 is a strong candidate for the optimal configuration.

Tab. 3. NPVs for the MSTES configurations

NPV [M\$]	France			Germany			Italy			Romania		
	S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3
U1L1											-82	
U2L1	-87	-90		-83	-83		-92	-92		-80	-65	
U3L1		-111	-130		-97			-110	-127		-105	-91
U1L2											-105	
U2L2		-87			-89		-99	-96		-108	-70	
U3L2		-115	-92		-97	-80		-116	-97		-112	-47

We continued this analysis by noting that the maximum increase in daily revenues is proportional to the area between the curves in fig. 3 and their respective averages. We noticed that the mentioned areas could be considered proportional to the daily variation in electricity prices. We proved this point by reporting in fig. 5 the area above (or below) the average electricity price for every day of 2023 for the considered countries on the x-axis, while on the y-axis the daily variation of electricity price. Thus, as a first approximation, we can say these two variables are proportional. Given this finding, we could also assume the presence of a similar proportionality between the increase in daily revenues and the daily variation of electricity prices. We investigated the minimum of such variation that makes the NPVs positive, i.e., the increase in revenues in the 1-day approximation needed to reach a positive NPV. Fig. 6 reports the results.

Fig. 5. Area above or below the average electricity price against its daily variation in 2023

Fig. 6. Variations in daily electricity prices to reach positive NPVs

We can see how the most expensive configuration in tab. 2, U3L2S3, requires the smallest variation in daily electricity prices to become profitable, at around 100 \$/MWh. All countries obtain similar values, ranging from 99 \$/MWh for France to 109 \$/MWh for Italy. These differences depend solely on electricity price variations. We can state that U3L2S3 is the most economically profitable configuration, and it will be the one considered for future computations. Such fluctuations in daily electricity prices were frequent in 2023, occurring approximately every 3-4 days (e.g., 97 instances in Italy that year). However, they are expected to become even more frequent as the share of intermittent renewable energy sources increases. Thus, future electricity prices may exhibit greater variability compared to those used in this analysis. In precisely such scenarios, MSTES demonstrates the greatest potential and economic performance. While it is possible to estimate future trends based on expected shares of electricity sources, we relied on already-known day-ahead prices, without uncertainty, to conduct a conservative evaluation. Additionally, future predictions may or may not be accurate depending on the Government policy as well.

For completeness we considered 4 random days of 2023 to perform the same calculations for configuration U3L2S3, with tab. 4 reporting the results. When the daily variations in electricity prices are over 100 \$/MWh, the increase in revenues could also be much higher than the expected maximum of 27-39 k\$/day for configuration U3L2S3. Sometimes this could happen also for lower daily variations if the electricity price profile is particularly favorable.

Tab. 4. Additional revenues obtained for 4 random 2023 days for configuration U3L2S3

<i>Configuration U3L2S3</i>		23rd January	8th April	10th August	17th October
France	<i>[k\$/day]</i>	54	24	21	35
	<i>Daily variation</i>	122	52	58	83
Germany	<i>[k\$/day]</i>	57	22	54	38
	<i>Daily variation</i>	124	46	167	94
Italy	<i>[k\$/day]</i>	44	32	20	25
	<i>Daily variation</i>	105	119	61	62
Romania	<i>[k\$/day]</i>	105	26	26	80
	<i>Daily variation</i>	235	70	94	200

3.2 Additional comments and results

In this section, we provide additional comments to conclude the economic analysis of MSTES. We relaxed some of the assumptions mentioned above and explored other aspects related to MSTES, in particular:

- Size limitations of the molten salt tanks: these define the upper bound for the maximum energy that can be stored with molten salt [1]. In the analyses above, ALFRED fully utilizes the MSTES, meaning that under a 1-day approximation, the tanks may get almost full and/or empty. For larger NPPs, such sizes might not be enough, requiring either additional tanks or an alternative storage technology.
- Extending the 1-day approximation: a more refined approach could involve a '2-day' approximation, which would partially restore the seasonality of electricity prices. Particularly, one day would represent the warm seasons (spring and summer), while the other would represent the cold seasons (autumn and winter), covering 184 and 181 days, respectively. We performed the analysis for U3L2S3 while keeping all other variables unchanged. The resulting NPVs were -82 M\$ for France, -66 M\$ for Germany, -90 M\$ for Italy, and -28 M\$ for Romania. This indicates that simply extending the analysis to two days leads to improvements in NPVs.
- Impact of interest rate changes: we originally assumed an interest rate of 5% for all countries, but this parameter can vary significantly, affecting the project's economic feasibility. To assess this impact, we performed the DCF for U3L2S3 with an increased interest rate of 7%. The results were -101 M\$ for France, -91 M\$ for Germany, -106 M\$ for Italy, and -64 M\$ for Romania. The negative effect of a higher interest rate is visible.
- Lifespan considerations: the lifespan of the LFR could be twice that of the MSTES. At the end of its lifespan, the MSTES could be dismantled and rebuilt, particularly if, at the 30-year mark, its NPV is positive. Alternatively, we could evaluate the implications of extending the MSTES lifespan to 60 years. This could be achieved through an initial 60-year license or a lifetime extension, as is common for NPPs. For the best-performing configuration (U3L2S3), we performed the DCF for 60 years. The results were -72 M\$ for France, -56 M\$ for Germany, -79 M\$ for Italy, and -14 M\$ for Romania, showing a significant improvement compared to the previous 30-year analysis.

4 Economic Analysis of LFRs coupled with High-Temperature Steam Electrolysis plants

The configurations considered here are those detailed in [2], with a total of 4. Tab. 5 summarizes the main characteristics of such configurations. They are called H1, H2, H3, and H4, with the number indicating the amount of HTSE modules that are present. The maximum number of modules is 4; 5 modules would require an electricity supply exceeding ALFRED's output.

Tab. 5. Main characteristics of the configurations of ALFRED coupled with HTSE plants [2]

	Unit	H1	H2	H3	H4	No H ₂ plant
Cycle gross power	MWe	127.1	125.5	123.8	122.2	128.5
HTSE required electric power	MWe	26.9	53.8	80.7	107.6	-
HTSE required thermal power	MWth	6.1	12.2	18.3	24.3	-
Power to the grid	MWe	89.5	60.9	32.4	3.8	118.9
Secondary water-derived mass flow	kg/s	2.41	4.83	7.24	9.65	-
H₂ production rate	kg/s	0.203	0.406	0.609	0.812	-
Electricity not sold during H₂ production	MWe	29.4	58.0	86.5	115.1	-
Electricity not sold during hot-standby	MWe	1.4	3.0	4.7	6.3	-
Overall efficiency	%	39.40	39.47	39.54	39.60	39.63

The methodology and the assumptions of this economic analysis could be summarized as follows:

- *Reference plant.* The base plant is ALFRED NPP by itself, not coupled with the HTSE plant. This is the base value, or 'zero', of the following economic analysis. In this analysis we are considering cogeneration of hydrogen, meaning the reactor can maintain a constant thermal power.
- *Cost estimation.* This analysis is based on a bottom-up cost estimation for the hydrogen plant. We considered HTSE pre-construction costs, DC (structures and improvements, HTSE equipment, thermal oil circuit, and other equipment), IC (site preparation, engineering and design, and fees), and its O&M costs. The HTSE plant is considered a FOAK. We estimated these costs from data and models found in the literature.
- *Countries.* We considered the hourly electricity prices from 2019 to 2023 (a span of 5 years) for France, Germany, Italy, and Romania, resulting in a total of 16 scenarios (4 configurations across 4 countries).
- *Hydrogen production hours.* Hydrogen is produced during the lowest electricity price hours. When not producing hydrogen, the HTSE plant remains in hot standby and still requires some electricity (tab. 5). We adopted an enumerative approach considering production times ranging from 1 to 43824 hours (spanning 5 years). This allowed us to determine the optimal production time that minimizes hydrogen costs.
- *Hydrogen production cost.* This is the sum of two components, both expressed in \$/kg. The first is the cost component, which includes CAPEX and OPEX of the hydrogen plant, here called C_{costs} . The second is the electricity component, which takes into account the opportunity cost, i.e., the loss

of revenues caused by the electricity not sold to the grid but used to produce hydrogen, this component is called $C_{electricity}$. The minimum value of this sum, at a specific production time, determines the minimum hydrogen production price and time. We assume that the NPP does not change its CAPEX and OPEX among the configurations.

Regarding this last point, at first, we computed the Total Produced Hydrogen (TPH, expressed in kg) in any arbitrary period. Each HTSE module produces 0.203 kg/s or 730.8 kg/h of hydrogen. We can multiply this rate by the considered hours and the number of HTSE modules, from 1 to 4. The contributions of CAPEX and OPEX decrease with hydrogen production. We assume that each year, hydrogen sales must at least cover the annual O&M costs (the term B in eq. 1) and a fraction of the TCI and its interests (the term A in eq. 1), considering the payments for the CAPEX and its interests as evenly spread over the HTSE lifetime [18]. Also, we need to account for the interest rate i (5%, the same for each country) to address the time dependencies of cash flows. Considering a period t for 5 years, as the considered electricity price data, we can write eq. 1 for the CAPEX and OPEX cost component of hydrogen production cost, C_{costs} :

$$C_{Costs} = \frac{t}{TPH} (A + B) \quad 1$$

Where A is computed by eq. 2 as reported in [18], considering an HTSE plant lifetime n for 20 years:

$$A = CAPEX \cdot \frac{i}{1 - (1+i)^{-n}} = CAPEX \cdot \frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1} \quad 2$$

The second component of hydrogen production cost (the term B from eq. 1) comes from the opportunity cost which depends on the electricity price, $C_{electricity}$. In principle, hydrogen production will occur during the period of lowest electricity prices. However, as TPH rises, the production of hydrogen occurs at progressively higher electricity costs. This component is computed with eq. 3:

$$C_{Electricity} = \left(P_{loss,H_2} \sum_{j=0}^{t_{H_2}} E_j + P_{loss,HSB} \sum_{j=t_{H_2}+1}^{43824} E_j \right) \frac{1}{TPH} \quad 3$$

where:

- P_{loss,H_2} indicates the electrical power not sold during hydrogen production;
- $P_{loss,HSB}$ indicates the electrical power not sold during hot-standby;
- t_{H_2} is the total time to produce the TPH in hours;
- E is the electricity price for a specific hour. Based on the assumptions mentioned earlier, we have $E_1 < E_2 < E_3 < \dots < E_{43824}$.

The sum of these components creates a curve with a minimum corresponding to the optimal production that minimizes hydrogen costs. We repeated this procedure for each configuration and country, a total of 16 times.

$$C_{hydrogen} = C_{Costs} + C_{electricity} \quad 4$$

We can now report the results of the analysis. The TCI for the HTSE plant is between 86 and 197 M\$ as reported in the tab. 6, its annual O&M would be between 11 and 26 M\$, both increasing with the number of modules. These values are assumed independent of the country. From the obtained values

and eq. 1, we can compute the first component, C_{costs} . We found if production time is lower than 2000 hours per year, hydrogen becomes too expensive, exceeding 8 \$/kg. On the other hand, beyond 5000 hours per year, the reduction in this cost component becomes marginal, stabilizing at around 1.5-2 \$/kg. The general curve for C_{costs} for configuration H4 can be seen in fig. 7.

Tab. 6. Results of the cost estimation for the different configurations

[M\$]	H1	H2	H3	H4
<i>Pre-construction costs (PC)</i>	1	2	2	3
<i>Direct costs (DC)</i>	60	91	117	139
<i>Indirect costs (IC)</i>	24	36	47	55
Total capital investment (TCI = PC+DC+IC)	86	130	166	197
Annual O&M costs	11	17	22	26

The second component, $C_{electricity}$, represents the opportunity cost which varies only slightly among configurations in specific terms (i.e., per kg of hydrogen produced) and is shown in fig. 7. With increased electricity consumption, hydrogen production also increases. As illustrated in fig. 7, this component is high (over 5 \$/kg) at low production levels (below 500 hours per year) because the small amount of hydrogen produced must compensate for the opportunity cost of the hot standby period. This component reaches a minimum of 2-3 \$/kg for a production period of 3000-4000 hours per year. For a longer production period, the opportunity cost rises, as hydrogen is produced using increasingly expensive electricity that the NPP could otherwise sell to the grid.

The sum of these two contributions gives the hydrogen production cost. Interestingly, the hydrogen cost curves reach their minima at 16-18 hours per day (or 5800-6600 hours per year), as shown for the general case of configuration H4 in fig. 7. Producing hydrogen continuously would increase its cost by approximately 25-30%. We found that the most expensive configuration, H4, actually has the lowest hydrogen production cost and optimal production time, ranging from 4-6 \$/kg at 16-18 hours per day, depending on the country. Tab. 7 reports the optimal production time and minimum hydrogen costs. This plant can produce up to 1-2% of the world's low-carbon hydrogen based on 2023 production level, which is expected to rise rapidly [7]. These values could increase for a FOAK plant due to factors such as higher initial costs, imperfect load factors, and not optimal production caused by limited knowledge of future electricity prices. The results are in the ballpark or lower than the ones obtained from other nuclear or renewables, but are still higher than fossil fuel-based production [19].

Fig. 7. General hydrogen production cost curve for configuration H4: the sum of the CAPEX and OPEX component (C_{cost}) and opportunity cost one ($C_{electricity}$)

Tab. 7. Optimal hydrogen production time that minimizes costs for configuration H4

Country	Optimal production time [h/day]	Minimum hydrogen production cost [\$/kg]
France	17.0	4.8
Germany	17.5	4.6
Italy	16.5	5.6
Romania	18.0	4.6

We perform a sensitivity analysis on the best-performing configuration, H4 in Romania; however, our findings apply and are true to any scenario. We found that the greatest impact on hydrogen production cost comes from the overall plant efficiency and the HTSE power requirements during production. HTSE CAPEX, OPEX, and interest rate have a lower impact for the same percentage variation, though they could also be subject to greater fluctuations. This could be a positive aspect as HTSE technology is still in its development phase. As the technology readiness level (TRL) increases, overall process efficiency is expected to improve, leading to lower power requirements. A certain percentage increase in overall efficiency translates into a similar reduction in hydrogen production cost. Fig. 8 illustrates the percentage variation from the optimal value considering a 10% variation of the inputs.

Fig. 8. Percentage reduction of hydrogen production cost after a 10% variation of the variables.

We also analyzed the case of larger LFR NPPs, i.e., with greater electrical power capacity, which would allow for a higher number of HTSE modules. Specifically, a 300 MWe LFR NPP can support a 10-module HTSE plant, while a 600 MWe LFR NPP can accommodate up to 20 modules. However, even with 10 or 20 modules, hydrogen production cost would not fall below 3 \$/kg, making it still not competitive compared to current fossil fuel-based production. Thus, economy-of-scale would be very beneficial but it would likely not be enough to have an economically competitive hydrogen production cost from LFRs against fossil fuel.

Possible ways to improve its economic competitiveness include tax reform and/or policy incentives. A Government interested in developing low-carbon hydrogen could impose taxes on greenhouse gas emissions, thereby increasing the cost of hydrogen produced from fossil fuels. This would also push plant owners to invest in carbon capture technology to mitigate emissions. Additionally, the Government could incentivize hydrogen production from low-carbon sources by offering tax credits, or long-term purchase agreements, making it more cost-competitive. Ultimately, policy interventions are essential for low-carbon hydrogen to compete with fossil fuel-based production.

5 Conclusion

Different economic analyses regarding the LFRs technology and its demonstrator (ALFRED) were performed. At first, we conducted a literature review highlighting the significant uncertainties surrounding this topic. Our findings indicate that reported values for the specific capital cost and levelized cost of electricity vary widely in the literature, ranging from 1.5-25 k\$/kWe and 30-350 \$/MWh, respectively. At this stage, providing a reliable estimate of these values, is nearly impossible, except in comparison with conventional NPPs, due to the lack of experience in building and operating LFRs.

We also conducted an economic analysis for MSTES integrated in an LFR BOP, based on ALFRED configurations. Our focus was on assessing the economic merit of the MSTES, evaluating CAPEX and OPEX, and using a DCF analysis to calculate the NPV of adding the additional plant. All results yielded negative NPVs. To be profitable, these plants require a daily electricity price variation of at least 100 \$/MWh. These variations are already common but would happen more often with an increasing share of intermittent renewable energy sources. The best configurations are the largest ones, due to economy-of-scale. However, to accommodate larger MSTES, the NPP would need either additional salt tanks or a change in the storage technology.

We also analyzed the hydrogen production cost through cogeneration in LFRs using HTSE. The assessment included the costs of the HTSE plants and the opportunity cost of producing hydrogen instead of selling electricity. The most favorable cost estimates range between 4-6 \$/kg, making it comparable with renewables but still higher than fossil fuel-based production. The optimal production time, to minimize hydrogen costs is around 16-18 hours/day. A sensitivity analysis was performed, highlighting the importance of the overall efficiency of the HTSE plant (an area still under research and development). We extended the analysis to larger plants, with additional HTSE modules. Hydrogen production cost is reduced due to economy-of-scale, but it is still higher than fossil-based production. Thus, for hydrogen from LFRs to become competitive, policy changes, tax reforms, or financial incentives would be necessary.

6 References

- [1] M. Celador Lera et al., 'D5.1 LFR BOP Configurations analysis: definition of the final system configuration, equipment specifications and balance of plant'. ANSELMUS D5.1, 2023. [LINK](#)
- [2] M. Celador Lera et al., 'D5.2 LFR BOP Main components definition: definition and sizing of the main components, including sensitivity analysis of both BOP configurations'. ANSELMUS D5.2, 2023. [LINK](#)
- [3] F. Tassone et al., 'Economics and finance of lead fast reactors: A systematic literature review'. Progress in Nuclear Energy 174 (2024) 105298. [DOI](#)
- [4] F. Tassone et al., 'Economic analysis of thermal energy storage integration in small modular reactors balance of plant'. IAEA 1st International Conference on Small Modular Reactors and Their Applications, Vienna, Austria, 21-25 October 2024. [LINK](#)
- [5] ENTSOE Transparency Platform website. [WEBSITE](#)
- [6] V. Amezcua Pérez, 'MS23 Definition of appropriate inputs for BoP and market to enable the economic and financial analysis'. ANSELMUS MS23, 2023.
- [7] M. Lambert et al., '2024 State of the European Hydrogen Market Report'. The Oxford Institute for Energy Studies, 2024. [LINK](#)
- [8] J. Guidez. 'Phénix: The feedback experience'. 2012.
- [9] World Nuclear Association. 'Russia - World nuclear performance report'. 2024. [LINK](#)
- [10] Newcleo website. [WEBSITE](#)
- [11] Fxtop.com website. [WEBSITE](#)
- [12] M. Shamoushaki et al., 'Development of cost correlations for the economic assessment of power plant equipment'. Energies 14 (2021) 2665. [DOI](#)
- [13] D. E. Holcomb et al., 'Advanced high temperature reactor systems and economic analysis'. ORNL/TM-2011/364, 2011. [LINK](#)
- [14] R. Smith, 'Chemical process design and integration'. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd. 2005. [LINK](#)
- [15] S. Thaker et al. 'Techno-economic evaluation of solar-based thermal energy storage systems'. Energy Conversion and Management 153 (2017), 423-434. [DOI](#)
- [16] W. Ding and T. Bauer. 'Progress in research and development of molten chloride salt technology for next generation concentrated solar power plants'. Engineering 7 (2021), 334-347. [DOI](#)
- [17] B. Kelly and D. Kearney. 'Thermal storage commercial plant design study for a 2-tank indirect molten salt system'. NREL/SR-550-40166. 2006. [LINK](#)
- [18] Investopedia. 'Equated monthly installment (EMI): How it works, formula, examples'. 2021. [LINK](#)
- [19] IAEA, 'Hydrogen production using nuclear energy'. NP-T_4.2. 2013. [LINK](#)

7 Appendix

In this section, we report in detail the estimation of costs for the MSTES plants. Tab. [A1](#) and [A2](#) report configuration data from [\[2\]](#) and other values (used or computed) from other references. Underlined values from the tab. [A2](#) are those directly reported by reference; the others are computed from the available data. Tab. [A3](#) reports the code of accounts for the MSTES plants integrated with ALFRED.

Tab. A1. Configuration data [\[2\]](#)

Variable	Value	Variable	Value
Total salt inventory S1 [ton]	12000	Number of salt pump units	3
Total salt inventory S2 [ton]	15000	Number of water pump units	2
Total salt inventory S3 [ton]	20000	Area de-superheater L1 [m ²]	5810
Tank height [m]	14,2	Area de-superheater L2 [m ²]	8750
Tank diameter S1 [m]	24,2	Area condenser L1 [m ²]	1190
Tank diameter S2 [m]	27,1	Area condenser L2 [m ²]	2480
Tank diameter S3 [m]	31,3	Area superheater U1 [m ²]	346
<i>Surface of carbon steel S1 [m²]</i>	<i>1999,5</i>	Area superheater U2 [m ²]	645
<i>Surface of carbon steel S2 [m²]</i>	<i>2362,6</i>	Area superheater U3 [m ²]	1200
<i>Surface of carbon steel S3 [m²]</i>	<i>2935,2</i>	Area evaporator U1 [m ²]	453
Tank volume S1 [m ³]	6543	Area evaporator U2 [m ²]	905
Tank volume S2 [m ³]	8179	Area evaporator U3 [m ²]	1800
Tank volume S3 [m ³]	10905	Area economiser U1 [m ²]	464
Cold salt pump power L1 [kWe]	165,49	Area economiser U2 [m ²]	872
Cold salt pump power L2 [kWe]	330,98	Area economiser U3 [m ²]	1660
Hot salt pump power U1 [kWe]	128,71	Tube material for heat exchangers: stainless steel	
Hot salt pump power U2 [kWe]	294,20	Shell material for heat exchangers: carbon steel	
Hot salt pump power U3 [kWe]	956,15		

Tab. A2. Data retrieved from other references

Variable	Value
Reference	[16]
Solar salt cost [\$/kg]	<u>0,5-0,8</u>
Used salt price [\$/ton]	800
Reference	[11]
From 2002 USD to 2022 USD	1,4163
From 2004 USD to 2022 USD	1,5284
From 2009 USD to 2022 USD	1,1954

From 2020 USD to 2022 USD	1,0899
Reference	[12]
Factory cost of shell and tube heat exchangers given area (m2)	$C_{HX} = \log(A) - 0,06395A^2 + 947A + 227,9$
Factory cost of water pump given power (kWe)	$C_p = \log(P) - 0,03195P^2 + 467,2P + 20480$
Reference	[13]
Site labor cost - feedwater heating system - pag 65 - FOAK	17112917
Site materials cost - feedwater heating system - pag 65 - FOAK	1703455
Total cost - feedwater heating system - pag 65 - FOAK	37796750
Ratio labor/factory cost	0,453
Ratio site material/factory cost	0,045
Turbine generator cost - FOAK	330612022
Turbine generator cost - NOAK	321562255
FOAK coefficient used for Acc. 231	1,028
Total turbine plant equipment - pag 32 - FOAK	266443824
Instrumentation and control	4483296
Reference	[14]
Material factor for carbon steel tube	0,58824
Temperature factor (>300°C)	1,60
Pressure factor (>50 bar)	1,50
Pressure factor (>100 bar)	1,90
Wall thickness (also dome and bottom) [m]	0,01
Carbon steel cost [\$/kg]	4,40
Reference	[17]
Balance of storage system (unloading 2h) [2002\$]	1165000
Balance of storage system (unloading 4h) [2002\$]	1836000
Balance of storage system (unloading 9h) [2002\$]	3596000
Balance of storage system (unloading 12h) [2002\$]	4785000
Installation labor time for salt pump (small) [h]	900
Installation labor time for salt pump (large) [h]	1500
Installation cost for (small) pump @ 40\$/h	36000
Installation cost for (large) pump @ 40\$/h	60000

Regarding the code of account, the following notes are considered:

A. Accounts 21 and 26 are 25% and around 5,5% of account 2. We can consider all the other accounts to write:

- Account 21 is 25% / (1-25%) of the accounts 22 to 26, the fraction is 0,333;
- Account 25 is 5,5% / (1-5,5%) of the accounts 21 to 25, the fraction is 0,058.

- B. The estimation of Account 223 is performed from [\[17\]](#). It is assumed equal to the value corresponding to the nearest amount of unloading hours.
- C. From [\[15\]](#), we obtained that Account 3 is 25.6% of the DC, which is the sum of Accounts 1, 2, and 3. Thus, Account 3 could be considered $0,256/(1-0,256)$ of Accounts 1 and 2. This fraction is 0,3441.
- D. All the costs are inserted in the last four columns (one for each configuration). All the used values and equations are reported in tab. [A1](#) and [A2](#).

Tab A3. Code of account used for estimation of MSTES costs

<u>ACCOUNT</u>	<u>METHOD OF ESTIMATION</u>	<u>DATA</u>	<u>MODEL</u>				
1 Capitalized pre-construction costs	Not considered as in [13]		0	0	0		
2 Capitalized direct cost	Sum of Acc. 21, 22, 23, 24, 25 and 26		Configuration	S1	S2	S3	
			U1L1	6.01E+07	6.77E+07	8.46E+07	
			U1L2	6.70E+07	7.38E+07	9.07E+07	
			U2L1	6.32E+07	7.12E+07	8.10E+07	
			U2L2	6.93E+07	7.73E+07	8,71E+07	
			U3L1	7.45E+07	8.04E+07	9.13E+07	
21 Structures and improvements	Assumed 25% of DC based on data from [13], see Note A	Fraction of DC	0,333	Configuration	S1	S2	S3
				U1L1	1.41E+07	1.57E+07	1.97E+07
				U1L2	1.56E+07	1.72E+07	2.11E+07
				U2L1	1.47E+07	1.65E+07	1.88E+07
				U2L2	1.61E+07	1.80E+07	2.02E+07
				U3L1	1.73E+07	1.87E+07	2.12E+07
22 Thermal energy storage equipment	Sum of Acc. 221, 222, and 223			Configuration	S1	S2	S3
				U1	1.81E+07	2.30E+07	3.52E+07
				U2	1.56E+07	2.13E+07	2.84E+07
				U3	1.46E+07	1.88E+07	2.67E+07

221	Salt	Estimated from design data and literature	Salt inventory (S)	Tab. A1	$C_{221} = iSP$	11475840	14344800	19126400	
			Salt price [\$/ton] (P) [16]	800					
			Inflation (i) [11]	1,1954					
			Surface of carbon steel per tank (S)	Tab. A1					
			Number of tanks (n)	2					
222	Hot and cold tanks	Estimated from the cost of carbon steel	Wall thickness (t)	0,01	$C_{222} = inStdC(1 + f)$	1519756	1891864	2502865	
			Density of carbon steel [kg/m3] (d)	7840					
			Carbon steel cost [\$/kg] (c)	4,4					
			Fraction of insulation and foundation - estimated from [17] (f)	75%					
			Inflation (i) [11]	1,4163					
223	Safety systems, leak detection systems, instrumentation and control, other equipment, and miscellaneous items	Assumed equal to the nearest value in literature. See note B	Value in literature (c) [17]	Tab. A2	$C_{223} = ic$	U1	5093015	6776996	13553991
						U2	2600327	5093015	6776996
						U3	1649990	2600327	5093015
23	Loading system	Sum of Acc. 231, 232, and 233				Configurations	L1	L2	
							1,82E+07	2,28E+07	
231	Heat transfer system	Estimated from literature and corrected with factors	Area de-superheater and area condenser	Tab. A1	$C_{231} = iftTp(1 + a)(1 + L + m)(C_{hx} + uC_p)$	16267817	20113182		
			Water pump power	Tab. A1					
			Factory cost of the heat exchanger (C_{hx}) [12]	Tab. A2					

			Factory cost of the water pump (C_p) [12]	Tab. A2				
			Number of pumps (u)	2				
			Site labor fraction (L) [13]	Tab B				
			Material fraction (m) [13]	Tab. A2				
			Tube material factor (t) [14]	0,5883				
			Temperature factor (T) [14]	1,60				
			Pressure factor (p) [14]	1,90				
			Assumed increase from additional tubing (α)	L1 - 25% L2 - 30%				
			FOAK factor (f) [13]	1,028				
			Inflation (i) [11]	1,0899				
			Pump power (P) [kWe]	Tab. A1				
			Site labor cost [\$] (L) [17]	Tab. A2				
232	Cold salts pump	Model from literature [17] and corrected with factors	Material fraction (m) [13]	Tab. A2	$C_{232} = iu[14720(1 + m)P^{0,5512} + L]$	1233696	1782138	
			Number of units (u)	3				
			Inflation (i) [11]	1,5284				
233	Instrumentation and control	Assumption	Fraction of (231+232) estimated from [13]	0,04		700061	875812	
24	Unloading system	Sum of Acc. 241, 242, and 243			Configuration	U1	U2	U3
						6.91E+06	1.13E+07	20.7E+07
241	Heat transfer system	Estimated from literature and corrected with factors	Area superheater, area evaporator, and area economizer	Tab. A1		5202508	8053895	12716840

25	Electrical equipment	Assumed to be already considered in other accounts				0	0	0
					Configuration	S1	S2	S3
					U1L1	2.98E+06	3.32E+06	4.15E+06
					U1L2	3.28E+06	3.62E+06	4.45E+06
26	Miscellaneous equipment	Assumed 5,5% of DC based on data from [13], see Note A	Fraction of DC	0,058	U2L1	3.10E+06	3.49E+06	3.97E+06
					U2L2	3.40E+06	3.79E+06	4.27E+06
					U3L1	3.65E+06	3.94E+06	4.48E+06
					U3L2	3.95E+06	4.24E+06	4.78E+06
					Configuration	S1	S2	S3
					U1L1	1.56E+07	1.73E+07	2.17E+07
					U1L2	1.71E+07	1.89E+07	2.32E+07
3	Capitalized indirect costs	Fraction of DC, 25,6% [15]. See note C			U2L1	1.62E+07	1.82E+07	2.07E+07
		0,12 for contractor's costs		0,3441	U2L2	1.77E+07	1.98E+07	2.23E+07
		0,056 for owner's costs			U3L1	1.91E+07	2.06E+07	2.34E+07
		0,08 for fees, insurance, and other supplementary cost			U3L2	2.06E+07	2.21E+07	2.49E+07
					Configuration	S1	S2	S3
					U1L1	7.64E+07	8.50E+07	1.06E+08
					U1L2	8.41E+07	9.27E+07	1.14E+08
					U2L1	7.94E+07	8.94E+07	1.02E+08
					U2L2	8.71E+07	9.71E+07	1.09E+08
					U3L1	9.36E+07	1.01E+08	1.15E+08
					U3L2	1.01E+08	1.09E+08	1.22E+08
				The MSTES TCI is the sum of accounts 1, 2, and 3				

N1		Increase in capital cost for the NPP		Configuration	U1	U2	U3
					9.41E+06	1.70E+07	3.19E+07
The total increase in capital investment is the sum of accounts N1 and the MSTES TCI							
4		Annualized O&M and decommissioning costs		Configuration	S1	S2	S3
		Fraction of the DC or TCI		U1L1	3.06E+06	3.40E+06	4.25E+06
		Fraction of MSTES TCI [15], is equal for both variable and fixed O&M costs. Decommissioning not considered		U1L2	3.36E+06	3.71E+06	4.56E+06
		0,04		U2L1	3.18E+06	3.58E+06	4.07E+06
				U2L2	3.48E+06	3.88E+06	4.38E+06
				U3L1	3.74E+06	4.04E+06	4.59E+06
				U3L2	4.05E+06	4.34E+06	4.90E+06
N2		Increase in O&M cost for the NPP			0	0	0
		Assumed zero					